

Performance of Lactation Milk Yield and Weekly Test Day Milk Yield in HF X GIR Half Bred

D. R. Tambe¹, T. D. Sabale²

^{1,2}Department of Animal Husbandry and Dairy Science

Corresponding Author- D. R. Tambe

Abstract:

The data on milk production performance of 342 HF X Gir halfbreds were collected from records maintained at Research Cum Development Project on Cattle, Mahatma Phule Krishi Vidyapeeth, Rahuri (Maharashtra) for a period from year 1974 to 2013. Overall mean of 43 individual weekly test day milk yield varied from 3.16 ± 0.14 kg (WTDY43) to 13.52 ± 0.14 kg (WTDY5). The overall mean lactation milk yield was 3457.33 ± 41.79 kg. Effect of period of calving on all 43 weekly test day milk yield was significant ($P < 0.01$) except WTDY4. The influence of season and period of calving and age at first calving on lactation milk yield were significant ($P < 0.01$). Phenotypic correlations among all test day milk yield ranged from 0.086 (WTDY1 with WTDY24) to 0.49 (WTDY32 with WTDY33). In HF X Gir halfbred heritability of lactation milk yield was 0.91 ± 0.15 . The h^2 of weekly test day milk yield ranged from 0.10 ± 0.48 (WTDY) to 0.94 ± 0.44 (WTDY).

Key word: Milk, Lactation period, Gir, H. F. Lactation milk yield, Test day milk yield.

Material and Methods:

The present study was undertaken on milk production performance of 342 HF X Gir halfbreds having 1039 lactations and 14397 weekly test day milk yield by collecting data from pedigree, history and milk recording sheets maintained at Research Cum Development Project on Cattle, Mahatma Phule Krishi Vidyapeeth, Rahuri (Maharashtra) over a period of 40 years (1974 to 2013). Least squares means of weekly test day milk and lactation milk yield in HF x Gir halfbred were estimated by considering effects of season of calving, period of calving, lactation order and sire⁵. Duncan's Multiple Range Test (DMRT) was used to make pair wise comparison between the mean values⁷. The heritability of traits, phenotypic and genetic correlations among milk production traits were also worked out.

Results and Discussion:

Overall mean weekly test day milk yield and least squares means of lactation milk yield as affected by period of calving, season of calving, lactation order, age at first calving and sire in HF X Gir halfbred are given in Table 1 and 2. The overall mean weekly test day milk yield in HF X Gir halfbred varied from 3.16 ± 0.14 kg to 13.52 ± 0.14 kg recorded during 43rd and 5th weeks respectively. The results indicated that mean test milk yield gradually increased from 1st week (9.15 ± 0.13 kg) reaching peak during 5th week (13.52 ± 0.14 kg) of cows calved during P1 (4035.60 ± 68.87 kg) was kg) and thereafter, declined in same manner during succeeding weeks reaching lowest in 43rd week (3.16 ± 0.14 kg). Similar trend of weekly test day significantly higher than cows calved in P2 to P6 periods. The LMY of cows calved during P2 (3643.89 ± 71.11) was significantly higher than

cows calved milk yield was reported in Karan Fries⁹ and Sahiwal in P3 to P6 periods. The higher LMY during initial cows².

The period of calving exerted significant ($P < 0.01$) influence on weekly test day milk yield. These results were in accordance with those reported in Karan Fries cows⁶. The season of calving had non- significant effect on WTDY except in WTDY1 ($P < 0.05$). The variation due to age at first calving was non- significant in all weekly test day milk yield from WTDY1 to WTDY43. Similar results were reported in Karan Fries cows¹⁰. The overall least squares mean of lactation milk yield in HF X Gir halfbred was 3457.33 ± 41.79 kg. These results were in accordance with those noticed in HF X Deoni halfbred¹¹. The influence of period of calving on lactation milk yield was significant ($P < 0.01$). The DMRT revealed that lactation milk yield period (P1) than succeeding periods might be due to presence of cows of FG original group in that period which showed hetrotic effect.

Whereas, LMY declined during later period than initial period might be due to the reduced number of original FG cows and increased interbred in which there might have been reduced the hetrotic effect. In HF X Gir halfbred effect of season of calving on lactation milk yield was significant ($P < 0.01$). The results revealed that lactation milk yield (kg) of cows calved during season S2 (3567.24 ± 58.72) was significantly higher than cows calved in S1 (3343.39 ± 59.39) and at par with S3 (3461.27 ± 56.51) season. The higher LMY in cows calved during winter season might be due to abundant availability of green fodder to milking cows in winter.

Table1. Overall mean weekly test day milk yield in HF X Gir halfbred

Week	WTDY (Kg)	Week	WTDY (Kg)
WTDY ₁	9.15±0.13	WTDY ₂₃	8.37±0.11
WTDY ₂	11.21±0.14	WTDY ₂₄	8.16±0.11
WTDY ₃	12.30±0.14	WTDY ₂₅	7.91±0.11
WTDY ₄	13.13±0.14	WTDY ₂₆	7.64±0.12
WTDY ₅	13.52±0.14	WTDY ₂₇	7.38±0.12
WTDY ₆	13.45±0.14	WTDY ₂₈	7.20±0.11
WTDY ₇	13.13±0.14	WTDY ₂₉	6.96±0.11
WTDY ₈	12.64±0.14	WTDY ₃₀	6.73±0.12
WTDY ₉	12.24±0.14	WTDY ₃₁	6.50±0.11
WTDY ₁₀	11.87±0.14	WTDY ₃₂	6.26±0.12
WTDY ₁₁	11.55±.13	WTDY ₃₃	6.04±0.12
WTDY ₁₂	11.19±0.13	WTDY ₃₄	5.83±0.12
WTDY ₁₃	10.91±0.12	WTDY ₃₅	5.62±0.12
WTDY ₁₄	10.66±0.12	WTDY ₃₆	5.35±0.12
WTDY ₁₅	10.43±0.12	WTDY ₃₇	5.10±0.12
WTDY ₁₆	10.15±0.12	WTDY ₃₈	4.55±0.13
WTDY ₁₇	9.88±0.12	WTDY ₃₉	4.88±0.13
WTDY ₁₈	9.68±0.12	WTDY ₄₀	4.23±0.13
WTDY ₁₉	9.37±0.11	WTDY ₄₁	3.89±0.13
WTDY ₂₀	9.13±0.12	WTDY ₄₂	3.52±0.13
WTDY ₂₁	8.89±0.11	WTDY ₄₃	3.16±0.14
WTDY ₂₂	8.89±0.11		

The variation due to lactation order in LMY of HF X Gir halfbred was significant ($P < 0.01$). These results were in conformity with those reported in HF higher than A3 (3353.22 ± 67.02 kg) group thereby indicating that cows calving at young age produced significantly less milk, which might be due to the X Deoni halfbred¹¹. The LMY of cows in L (3810.27 Animals in this age group might not have attained ± 10.94 kg), L3 (3560.49 ± 71.05 kg) and L4 (3810.27 ± 104.94 kg) lactations was significantly higher than those of cows in L1 (2966.56 ± 54.51 kg) and L2 (3252.30 ± 62.48 kg) lactations, which did not differed significantly from each other. These results indicated that in HF X Gir halfbred LMY gradually Optimum age and body weight at calving. In HF X Gir halfbred phenotypic correlations among weekly test day milk yield were positive and significant which were low to moderate for different WTDY. Phenotypic correlations among all test day milk yield ranged from 0.086 (WTDY1 with WTDY24)

to 0.49 (WTDY32 increased from 1st lactation up to 5th lactation. with WTDY33). These results were in agreement with This might be attributed to their physiological development of body, milk secretory tissues and mammary gland with advancing age. Influence of age at first calving on lactation milk yield was significant ($P < 0.05$). Similar results were noticed in HF x Deoni crossbred³. The LMY of cows of A1 group (3582.69 ± 55.75 kg) was at par those reported in Gir triple cross cows⁸. The genetic correlations amongst various weekly test days milk yield ranged from 0.26 (WTDY8 with WTDY18) to 1.0 (WTDY12 with WTDY42). In present study very high, positive and significant genetic correlations was observed among WTDY. Present results were similar to the estimates of genetic correlations among test day milk yield reported in Holstein Friesian¹. with cows of A2 (3436.10 ± 77.78 kg) and significantly.

Table2. Least squares means of lactation milk yield in HF X Gir halfbred as affected by non-geneticfactors

Source of variation	n	LMY (kg)
Population mean (u)	1039	3457.33 ± 41.79
Period of calving		
P ₁ (1974-1980)	385	4035.60 ^a ± 68.87
P ₂ (1981-1987)	194	3643.89 ^b ± 71.11
P ₃ (1988-1994)	143	3145.25 ^d ± 79.67
P ₄ (1995-2001)	182	3428.52 ^c ± 69.90

P ₅ (2002-2008)	95	3141.95 ^d ± 10.02
P ₆ (2008 and above)	40	3378.81 ^c ± 15.69
Season of calving		
S ₁ (Rainy)	330	3343.39 ^b ± 59.39
S ₂ (Winter)	356	3567.34 ^a ± 58.72
S ₃ (Summer)	353	3461.27 ^{ab} ± 56.51
Lactation order		
L ₁	342	2966.56 ^c ± 54.51
L ₂	268	3252.30 ^b ± 62.48
L ₃	201	3560.49 ^a ± 71.05
L ₄	144	3697.05 ^a ± 82.01
L ₅	84	3810.27 ^a ± 104.94
Age at first calving		
A ₁ (<950)	629	3582.69 ^a ± 55.75
A ₂ (951-1050)	171	3436.10 ^{ab} ± 77.78
A ₃ (1051 and above)	239	3353.22 ^b ± 67.02

Means under each class in the same column with different superscripts differed significantly.

In HF X Gir halfbred heritability of lactation milk yield was 0.91 ± 0.15 . The h^2 of weekly test day Harvey W. R. 1990. Least-squares analysis of data with unequal subclass numbers. ARS H-4, milk yield ranged from 0.10 ± 0.48 (WTDY27) to 0.94 U. S. D.A., Washington. ± 0.44 (WTDY2). Higher heritability estimates were observed in middle segment than initial and later segment. In accordance with the present findings low to moderate heritability estimates were reported in Sahiwal cattle².

References:

1. Brotherstone, S., White, M.S. and Meyer, K. 2000. Genetic modeling of daily milk yield using orthogonal polynomials and parametric curves. *Indian J. Anim. Sci.*, 70 (2): 407-415.
2. Dongre, V. B. 2012. Modeling lactation curve for sire evaluation in Sahiwal cattle. *Ph. D. Thesis* submitted to NDRI, Karnal.
3. Gatchearle, P. L., Mitkari, K. R., Mule, R. S., Baswade, S. V. and Adangale, S. B. 2009. Effect of age at first calving on lactation milk yield and lactation length. *Indian J. Anim. Res.*, 43 (3): 228-229.
4. Hadge, M.R., Kuralkar, S.V., Ali, S.Z., Kharkar, K.P. and Sawaimul, A.D. 2012. Genetic studies on productive traits of Sahiwal and Jersey x Sahiwal crossbred cows. *Indian J. Anim. Res.* 46(1): 92-94.
5. Kokate, L. 2009. Genetic evaluation of Karan Fries sires based on test day milk yield records. *M. V. Sc. Thesis* submitted to NDRI, Karnal.
6. Kramer, C. V. 1957. Extension of multiple range test to group correlated adjusted mean. *Biometric.*, 13: 13-20.
7. Patond, M. N. 2013. Modelling of lactation curve in Gir triple cross cows. *Ph.D. Thesis* submitted to M. P. K. V., Rahuri.
8. Rashia Banu N. 2010. Genetic evaluation of the lactation curve in Karan Fries cattle. *Ph. D. Thesis* submitted to NDRI, Karnal.
9. Rose, K. 2008. Studies on lactation curve parameters for milk yield in Karan Fries animals. *M. V. Sc. Thesis* submitted to NDRI, Karnal.
10. Wondifraw, Z., Thombre, B. M. and Bainwad, D.V. 2013. Effect of non-genetic factors on milk production of HF x Deoni crossbred cows. *International J. Livestock Prod.* 4 (7): 106-112.